

EOSC POLICY BRIEF

CALL: HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ERA-01-41

TOPIC: GLOBAL COOPERATION ON FAIR DATA POLICY AND PRACTICE

PROJECT: GLOBAL COOPERATION ON FAIR DATA POLICY AND PRACTICE
(WORLDFAIR) [HTTPS://WORLDFAIR-PROJECT.EU/](https://worldfair-project.eu/)

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SCOPE OF THE POLICY BRIEF

In this policy brief, the projects contributing to the advancement of the European Open Science Cloud – EOSC – report on the progress made and provide recommendations to the European Commission for further policy analysis and development. This policy brief should be understood as complementary to the other mandatory reporting materials.

Policy background:

The European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) is recognised by the Council of the European Union as the pilot action to deepen the new [European Research Area \(ERA\)](#) and is included in the [ERA policy agenda 2022-2024](#). EOSC is also recognised in the [European strategy for data](#) as the data space for science, research and innovation which shall be fully articulated with the other sectoral data spaces defined in the strategy.

Overall progress is steered by the EOSC tripartite governance involving the Union represented by the European Commission, the participating countries represented in the EOSC Steering Board and the research community represented by the EOSC Association. The second phase of development of EOSC (2021-2030) takes place in the context of the EOSC European co-programmed Partnership, which brings together the European Commission and the EOSC Association according to the [Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda \(SRIA\)](#) which is co-developed with the entire EOSC community and sets three general objectives:

- 1. Open science becomes the ‘new normal’, by ensuring that open science practices and skills are rewarded and taught.*
- 2. Researchers can seamlessly find, access, reuse and combine results, through the definition of common standards and the development of related tools and services.*
- 3. A federated infrastructure under community governance enabling open sharing of scientific results is deployed and sustained.*

FEEDBACK ON PROGRESS

1: Contribution to the SRIA: ‘WorldFAIR: Global cooperation on FAIR data policy and practice’¹ is a two-year project to advance implementation of the FAIR principles,² particularly in relation to interoperability and reusability of data within and across research domains. With an explicit mission to advance global collaboration and include partners from outside the European Union, WorldFAIR is coordinated by CODATA,³ the Committee on Data of the International Science Council,⁴ with the Research Data Alliance (RDA) association⁵ as a major partner.

The project is conceived as responding to Recommendation 4 of the *Turning FAIR into Reality* report, which identified the need to ‘Develop interoperability frameworks for FAIR sharing within disciplines and for interdisciplinary research’. The Recommendation states that ‘Research communities need to be supported to develop interoperability frameworks that define their practices for data sharing, data formats, metadata standards, tools and infrastructure. To support interdisciplinary research, these interoperability frameworks should be articulated in common ways and adopt global standards where relevant.’⁶ It is this vision of enabling community agreements around interoperability, and encouraging the identification and adoption of common standards that drives the WorldFAIR project. This recommendation is cited in the SRIA⁷ (pp.55-6) and is fundamental to achieving the vision of EOSC and Open Science more generally.

WorldFAIR is working with a set of eleven domain and cross-domain Case Studies⁸, carefully chosen from existing CODATA and RDA activities to provide maximum impact. Each Case Study (in project terms, a ‘Work Package’) will develop an interoperability framework, recommendations and/or a FAIR implementation for their discipline or interdisciplinary research area. Led by CODATA, a coordinating and synthesis activity (Work Package 2) has been supporting each Case Study in understanding their requirements through the completion of FAIR Implementation Profiles (FIPs).⁹ In turn these insights will be incorporated into the development of a Cross-Domain Interoperability Framework (CDIF)¹⁰ and more domain-sensitive recommendations for FAIR assessment and benchmarks.¹¹

Each of these outputs—discipline-oriented interoperability frameworks and/or recommendations; a set of FIPs; a Cross-Domain Interoperability Framework and domain-sensitive recommendations for FAIR assessment—is relevant to the SRIA, and those parts of the SRIA that deal with the EOSC Interoperability Framework,¹² metadata and ontologies, and FAIR metrics and certification.

WorldFAIR is also relevant to the parts of the SRIA that deal with ‘facing global challenges through multi-disciplinary programmes’, the ‘diversity of FAIR practices’, and the need for ‘community standards’. In sum, the WorldFAIR project makes a significant contribution to the EOSC Interoperability Framework in two important respects. First, the project underlines, and puts into practice, the need to engage research disciplines, *at a global scale*, in the development of agreements and frameworks for FAIR. Second, the CDIF identifies a set of functional requirements to support FAIR and identifies existing or emerging standards and protocols that

¹ See <https://worldfair-project.eu/>

² Wilkinson, M., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I. et al. The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Sci Data* 3, 160018 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>

³ See <https://codata.org/>

⁴ See <https://council.science/>

⁵ See <https://www.rd-alliance.org/rda-europe>

⁶ European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, *Turning FAIR into reality: final report and action plan* from the European Commission expert group on FAIR data, Publications Office, 2018, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/1524>; p.29.

⁷ European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, *Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA) of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)*, Publications Office of the European Union, 2022, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/935288>

⁸ Listed at <https://worldfair-project.eu/case-studies-of-worldfair/>

⁹ See <https://www.go-fair.org/how-to-go-fair/fair-implementation-profile/>

¹⁰ See <https://worldfair-project.eu/cross-domain-interoperability-framework/>

¹¹ See <https://worldfair-project.eu/fair-assessment/>

¹² European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Corcho, O., Eriksson, M., Kurowski, K., et al., *EOSC interoperability framework : report from the EOSC Executive Board Working Groups FAIR and Architecture*, Publications Office, 2021, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/620649>

can be used across domains. The CDIF is categorically not a new standard intended to replace others, but a framework of existing cross-domain standards or emerging protocols, which will add significant detail and actionability to the EOSC Interoperability Framework.

2: Interactions and synergies with EOSC Stakeholders: WorldFAIR participates in the EOSC coordination meetings (September 2022 and June 2023). In January 2023, meetings were arranged with colleagues at DG RTD and with the EOSC Association. WorldFAIR has also participated in a number of meetings arranged by or through the EOSC Association on technical infrastructures and data spaces. A session on WorldFAIR, and specifically the use of FIPs, was organised at the EOSC Symposium, Prague, November 2022. The RDA Association is a major partner in the WorldFAIR project, leading the communications Work Package: thus, the activities of WorldFAIR and its Case Studies are being given visibility through sessions at the RDA plenary and webinar series. A well-attended event on the WorldFAIR project's Cross-Domain Interoperability Framework was held on 20 March 2023, co-located with the RDA Plenary in Gothenburg.

Simon Hodson (CODATA, project coordinator) and Hilde Orten (Sikt, WP06) are members of the EOSC-A Semantic Interoperability Task Force¹³ and efforts have been made to engage the current leadership of the TF (Kurt Baumann and Wolmar Nyberg Åkerström). A presentation on WorldFAIR will be given to the SI TF on 3 May 2023. CODATA and the RDA Association are partners in the FAIR-Impact project; discussions have been held with the technical leadership of EOSC-Core; CODATA is also a key partner in the RDA TIGER project, led by RDA Association. All these links will be used to encourage synergies where possible.

A number of the WorldFAIR Case Studies have connections with significant Horizon Europe Projects: WP04 Nanomaterials with NanoCommons¹⁴ and PARC¹⁵; WP06 Social Surveys partner Sikt is leading an EOSC Future Science Project on cross-domain data integration combining social surveys data with contextual environmental data; WP09 Biodiversity lead GBIF is involved in DISSCO¹⁶; WP11 Ocean Sciences lead is also a partner in Blue Cloud¹⁷; WP13 Cultural Heritage lead DRI has links to Europeana¹⁸.

3: Challenges: Funded through the WIDERA call channel, it is understood that WorldFAIR was overlooked for a first meeting of INFRA-EOSC projects in June 2022, and it may be that the global and international character of WorldFAIR leads to it being viewed as something of an outlier. Nevertheless, WorldFAIR will continue to make the case for the importance of EOSC engaging with international developments, organisations and stakeholders, particularly in the development of community practices, norms and standards.

WorldFAIR will continue to engage as much as possible with the EOSC-A and INFRA-EOSC projects and make the case for the domain recommendations and Cross-Domain Interoperability Framework that emerges.

4: Contribution of WorldFAIR: At the time of writing, WorldFAIR is preparing for the first project review after 9 months of activity. Intentionally, given the nature of the work and the engagement with a large range of Case Studies, many of the project's deliverables are due later in the project.

The WP02 coordination and synthesis activity, led by CODATA, has drawn attention to the utility of FIPs. The workshop 'FAIR Implementation Profiles (FIPs) in WorldFAIR: what have we learnt?'¹⁹ was attended by 50 people in person and 120 online. The report of the same name, D2.1, has been downloaded over 700 times.²⁰ We have been approached by a number of potential additional case studies that would like to be coached and supported in the process of creating FIPs.

The major contribution of the coordination and synthesis activity will be the proposed Cross-Domain Interoperability Framework (CDIF). Work on this is well underway, though the deliverable (D2.3) is not due until the very end of the project in month 24. The WorldFAIR project has communicated and advanced this activity through conference sessions, webinars and workshops. Most recently, the current thinking and

¹³ See <https://www.eosc.eu/advisory-groups/semantic-interoperability>

¹⁴ See <https://www.nanocommons.eu/>

¹⁵ See <https://worldfair-project.eu/2023/04/12/next-up-in-the-parc-fair-data-and-tools-webinar-series/>

¹⁶ See <https://www.dissco.eu/>

¹⁷ See <https://blue-cloud.org/>

¹⁸ See <https://pro.europeana.eu/organisation/digital-repository-of-ireland>

¹⁹ See <https://worldfair-project.eu/2023/03/22/the-worldfair-projects-cross-domain-interoperability-framework-2/>

²⁰ Gregory, Arofan, & Hodson, Simon. (2022). WorldFAIR Project (D2.1) 'FAIR Implementation Profiles (FIPs) in WorldFAIR: What Have We Learnt?' (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7378109>

progress was presented in the workshop co-located with the RDA Plenary, already mentioned above. Attended by over 60 people, in person and online, the workshop had a high level of engagement and has led directly to the presentation to the EOSC-A SI IF also mentioned above. Finally, WorldFAIR, the CDIF and three of the Case Studies also featured in a one-day symposium ‘Towards a FAIRer World’,²¹ organised with UNESCO, the International Science Council and the World Data System, attended by a global audience of 80 in-person and nearly 200 online²².

Each WorldFAIR Case Study will produce an interoperability framework, recommendations and/or a FAIR implementation Profile for their discipline or interdisciplinary research area. So far, four of the Case Studies have produced deliverables contributing towards this objective:

1. D5.1 Formalisation of OneGeochemistry²³: 114 downloads
2. D6.1 Cross-national Social Sciences survey FAIR implementation case studies²⁴: 324 downloads
3. D13.1 Cultural Heritage Mapping Report: Practices and policies supporting Cultural Heritage image sharing platforms²⁵: 549 downloads
4. D11.1 An assessment of the Ocean Data priority areas for development and implementation roadmap²⁶: 197 downloads

As we approach the project’s 12-month halfway mark, no fewer than 7 further deliverables are due by 31 May 2023:

1. D3.1 Digital recommendations for Chemistry FAIR data policy and practice
2. D4.1 Nanomaterials domain-specific FAIRification mapping
3. D7.1 Population Health Data Implementation Guide
4. D8.1 Urban Health Data - Guidelines and Recommendations
5. D9.1 Data standard for sharing ecological and environmental monitoring data documented for community review
6. D12.1 Disaster Risk Reduction Case Study report
7. D13.2 Cultural Heritage Recommendations

In sum, the WorldFAIR project will make a major contribution to FAIR policy and practice in 11 specific research areas, while proposing the Cross-Domain Interoperability Framework which will assist interdisciplinary research fields.

5: WorldFAIR Contribution to other EU Policy Priorities:

[Horizon Europe Missions](#) Cancer, Climate Change, Oceans, Climate neutral and Smart cities, Soil-deal for Europe

To a significant degree, the vision for WorldFAIR builds on CODATA’s work for the International Science Council’s Action Plan Project 2.1 ‘Making Data Work for Global Grand Challenges’. The Cross-Domain Interoperability Framework will be significant for increasing the FAIRness and utility of data for each of the priority areas listed, which are in their nature interdisciplinary.

The work of WorldFAIR WPs 7 (Urban Health), 11 (Ocean Science), and 12 (Disaster Risk Reduction) will have relevance for the Horizon Europe Missions ‘Climate Neutral and Smart Cities’, ‘Oceans’, and ‘Climate Change’ respectively.

²¹ See <https://codata.org/events/science-and-policy-workshops/towards-a-fairer-world/>

²² See <https://www.unesco.org/en/articles/towards-fairer-world-implementing-unesco-recommendation-open-science-address-global-challenges>

²³ Prent, Alexander. (2022). WorldFAIR Project (D5.1) Formalisation of OneGeochemistry (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7380947>

²⁴ McEachern, Steven, Orten, Hilde, Thome Petersen, Hanna, & Perry, Ryan. (2023). WorldFAIR Project (D6.1) Cross-national Social Sciences survey FAIR implementation case studies (1.1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7599652>

²⁵ Knazook, Beth, & Murphy, Joan. (2023). WorldFAIR Project (D13.1) Cultural Heritage Mapping Report: Practices and policies supporting Cultural Heritage image sharing platforms (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7659002>

²⁶ Buttegieg, Pier Luigi. (2023). WorldFAIR Project (D11.1) An assessment of the Ocean Data priority areas for development and implementation roadmap (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7682399>

1. Sufficiently Detailed, Standardised, and Interoperable Metadata

Data that are not sufficiently documented at a detailed level are not often reused even when made available, because they are not easy to understand or assess for their suitability for a specific (re)use. This is a consequence of insufficient detail in the documentation provided: data are only useful if the information needed to integrate them with other data exists. In cases where this level of information is provided, reuse of those data increases or becomes possible.²⁷

To be useful, a wider range of data needs to be located, accessed, and understood by the scientists performing the analysis. To be effectively integrated, the information about the data needs to be very detailed. Traditional practice, depending on a knowledge of the literature and the principal investigators within any given domain to find and reuse data, can no longer support these broad-based demands. Ultimately, we are faced with a challenge to produce better and more detailed metadata to support this broad form of data reuse, even while the volume of potentially high-value data is increasing. Existing practice in terms of data management is not equal to the task.

While much attention is paid to artificial intelligence (AI) as the most important emerging technology, the factor which most limits its use, at least in science, is a mundane one: **research data that are not sufficiently described cannot be used by any form of intelligence, artificial or otherwise**. Much of the effort that goes into AI approaches, in relation to scientific discovery, is only necessary because the provenance and detail regarding the research data being consumed have been discarded after its initial collection or generation. Good data stewardship, which preserves and publishes this detailed information about the data, will enable powerful AI techniques to realise their promise more fully, and support more effective use of traditional data analysis approaches as well.

A significant purpose of the FAIR principles was precisely to address this issue. The idea that better-managed data could be ubiquitously available through increases in automation and the use of modern information technology is an appealing one. It offers a solution to the increased ability to use, and demand for, data as a primary resource and reflects the broadened scope of research across domain boundaries. This vision of a FAIR data ecosystem provides a foundation on which the accompanying vision of open science can be realised.

Two use cases being explored by the WorldFAIR project very clearly illustrate **the need for sufficiently detailed, standardised, and interoperable metadata** to better enable more automated data integration, as well as cross-domain research employing AI and large-scale analysis. These are:

1. the need to better facilitate (and automate) data combination and analysis;
2. the need to automate fine-grained and responsive access control.

These two use cases are described further in relation to the other recommendations below. The implication, also explored further in the other recommendations, is the need for **a shift from a 'bibliographic' data stewardship practice to a data engineering practice**.

²⁷ Pasquetto, I. V., Borgman, C. L., & Wofford, M. F. (2019). Uses and Reuses of Scientific Data: The Data Creators' Advantage. *Harvard Data Science Review*, 1(2). <https://doi.org/10.1162/99608f92.fc14bf2d>

2. Enabling Community FAIR Practices

Technical standards that can communicate information about all aspects of data need to exist and be implemented, both at the level of domains *and* for the purposes of cross-domain exchange. Many domains have developed technical standards for metadata, and these are to varying extents adopted. Some domains are well organised regarding metadata exchange while others rely on the organic emergence of good practices which remain relatively ungoverned or are dominated by the implementations of major infrastructure players. The need for the development and governance of sufficient metadata standards—addressing the requirements both for granularity and for provenance—is clear.

The experience of the WorldFAIR Project’s FIPs exercise is illustrative here. As presented in our report ‘FAIR Implementation Profiles (FIPs) in WorldFAIR: What Have We Learnt?’,²⁸ the FIPs exercise was valuable in helping us better understand the complex data practices in each of the Case Study communities. The process and methodology were also useful in helping construct a picture encompassing both the current state of practice in relation to FAIR and the possible aspirations for greater FAIR implementation in the field of research of each Case Study.

Looking towards what is required to support machine-actionable exchange of data not across individual infrastructures, but across broader communities, the report called for the following actions to be taken:

1. Better defining what constitutes a ‘community of practice’ for FAIR implementation, to ensure that improvements in the shareability of data can be realised;
2. Identifying meaningful levels of FAIRness, based on existing practice and building toward more complete support for all aspects of FAIR (starting with ‘Findability’ and proceeding from there), in concrete terms;
3. Establishing strategies for building on existing metadata holdings and data management and dissemination practices, and working step-wise toward more complete support;
4. Identifying or organising ‘standards bodies’ which are recognised as authoritative, and which can develop, endorse and maintain standards for the communities identified in cases where these do not already exist.²⁹

Support for the adoption and use of such technical standards must also exist, as such standards represent the specific technologies needed to enable the emergence of a more granular culture around data management. Mechanisms (specifically infrastructures and practices) are required for the effective communication of data and metadata among user communities. Illustrative of this point are the recommendations made in the WorldFAIR WP06 report on ‘Cross-National Social Sciences Survey: FAIR implementation case studies’, which identifies the need for harmonisation of practices and international infrastructures. The report calls for:

- The adoption of the Data Documentation Initiative (DDI) variable cascade³⁰ across (social survey) infrastructures internationally, to assist with data harmonisation and integration.
- The creation of public repositories of template scripts used for data harmonisation and integration.
- The creation of registries of common variables and other reusable metadata and content.

“Where possible, common content such as harmonised variables and code mappings should be persistently identified and made available through such registries to enable standardised and reusable harmonisation practices”.³¹

²⁸ Gregory, Arofan, & Hodson, Simon. (2022). WorldFAIR Project (D2.1) 'FAIR Implementation Profiles (FIPs) in WorldFAIR: What Have We Learnt?' (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7378109>

²⁹ Gregory, Arofan, & Hodson, Simon. (2022). WorldFAIR Project (D2.1) 'FAIR Implementation Profiles (FIPs) in WorldFAIR: What Have We Learnt?' (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7378109>, pp.24-25.

³⁰ See [Webinar: The DDI Variable Cascade: Describing Data to Optimize Reusability and Comparison](#) and [DDI-CDI: Optimising Your Data Description for Integration and Reuse, Workshop 24 March 2023](#).

³¹ McEachern, Steven, Orten, Hilde, Thome Petersen, Hanna, & Perry, Ryan. (2023). WorldFAIR Project (D6.1) Cross-national Social Sciences survey FAIR implementation case studies (1.1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7599652>, pp.21-22.

3. Cross-Domain Data Combination

The major global human, societal, environmental and scientific challenges of our age are fundamentally interdisciplinary and related to all sectors of society. These challenges can *only* be addressed through the close collaboration of science, civil society, and government using cross-domain and multi-stakeholder research that seeks to understand complex systems through machine-assisted analysis, and enables data-driven decision-making processes.³² The ability to combine data across traditional disciplines is becoming a *sine qua non* for many areas of research. As noted above, this can only be achieved by the collaborative development, refinement and international adoption of **sufficiently detailed, fine-grained, standardised, and interoperable metadata**.

Research as a culture is increasingly embracing these changes: projects which are cross-cutting in nature, involving data coming from a range of disciplines, are more common than in the past. When we consider topics such as the COVID pandemic or climate change, we can see that understanding these phenomena demands a broad range of data in different areas. To be useful, this data needs to be integrated, allowing for coherent conclusions to be drawn from it. One clear example of this is OneBioSecurity³³.

WorldFAIR and other recent efforts within EOSC are also demonstrating some of the approaches which can be taken to enrich documentation and metadata to support broader data reuse, particularly across domain boundaries. One major element of such enrichment is better provenance and processing metadata: what source data has been used, and how it has been processed to make it compatible with other data for integration? Environmental data can be combined with social data, but such integration is demanding and must be well-described so that researchers in different domains can make practical use of it. Similar examples include combinations of social survey data with economic and health data: projects such as EOSC Future WP6.3, Science Project 9 are exploring the specific issues around this type of integration.³⁴

The inclusion of information about time and geography in data are central and go beyond the simple inclusion of coverage description. Semantic and methodological information is also essential to avoid ambiguity. Good semantic information addresses cases where different terms can mean similar things and the same term can have multiple meanings even in related domains (for instance, the term ‘community’ will probably refer to different concepts in an ecological study than in an anthropological one). Methodological information—especially as it concerns the processing of collected data—can also defy easy integration. These types of information will ultimately affect interpretation, both by humans and machines.

In terms of cross-domain standards, many already exist through bodies such as the World Wide Web Consortium (W3C). In many cases, however, it is not evident how best the available technology solutions can be employed. In WorldFAIR an effort is being made to develop recommendations for how existing standards can be used in a coordinated fashion to facilitate cross-domain exchange of data and metadata. This set of recommendations is known as the Cross Domain Interoperability Framework (CDIF).³⁵

The CDIF idea comes out of several years of discussion and related work and is conceived as a set of recommendations for the coordinated use of standards to enable automated, cross-domain sharing of data and metadata. The idea is that by establishing a ‘lingua franca’ based on existing cross-domain standards, it will become possible to implement cross-domain exchange of FAIR metadata and data—including data discovery, access, and integration—in a scalable fashion. In the simplest terms, CDIF would be a recommended practice for implementing relevant standards, to support the needed interchange of data and metadata. WorldFAIR has established a Working Group and Advisory Group which are in the process of developing these recommendations. Iterations will be discussed at various venues through 2023 and a first framework will be submitted as a WorldFAIR project deliverable in May 2024.³⁶

³² See for example, the International Science Council’s Action Plan, area 2.1: <https://council.science/actionplan/making-data-work-for-grand-challenges/>

³³ Philip E. Hulme; One Biosecurity: a unified concept to integrate human, animal, plant, and environmental health. *Emerg Top Life Sci* 15 December 2020; 4 (5): 539–549. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1042/ETLS20200067>

³⁴ See Orten, H. and Agasøster, B.: Cross Domain Interoperability in Science Project 9 of EOSC Future WP6.3, EGU General Assembly 2023, Vienna, Austria, 24–28 Apr 2023, EGU23-2047, <https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu23-2047> and <https://eddi22.sciencesconf.org/424448>

³⁵ See the Cross Domain Interoperability Framework (CDIF) - <https://worldfair-project.eu/cross-domain-interoperability-framework/>

³⁶ See Gregory, Arofan, & Hodson, Simon. (2023). Cross-Domain Interoperability Framework (CDIF) Working Documents. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7652742>

4. Fine-Grained Access Control

In many circumstances, access to data must be controlled. When data are only managed as monolithic ‘sets’ of data, they are less likely to be reused since a single disclosive variable—one which can lead to the unintended identification of a subject which must remain anonymous—can ‘poison’ the entire data set. In systems in which entire files, or small collections of files, are the object to which access rights are assigned, the ‘access boundary’ is necessarily limited to letting the most confidential and/or sensitive variables determine the access level to the whole package. For example, if we have a file containing 200 variables, of which two contain potentially sensitive, personal or disclosive information, then the entire file must be ruled off-limits for those who do not have sufficient access privileges. This phenomenon is termed ‘data poisoning’: that is, 198 of the 200 variables must be restricted (quarantined) for many legitimate users because of the ‘toxic’, disclosive nature of only two variables and through which they have been ‘infected’. The real-world consequences of this are increased access times to data for end-users, and complex administrative overheads for data providers, with locally defined, often human-mediated workflows, which cannot scale up in the long term. **A significant limiting factor, therefore, is the inability to automate the negotiation of data access, which—while difficult—has been shown to be feasible in cases where sufficiently granular metadata exists.**

What we can understand from this is that the existing culture of data management, which often views the ‘data set’ as a monolithic entity acting as an adjunct to the publications it underpins, is a barrier to secondary data use. Data can be viewed as a primary resource, and indeed needs to be, but this will require a change in how it is managed, described, parsed and made available.

Some interesting steps are also being taken in relation to the automation of access control, although these are less well developed. The UK Data Archive and others have been exploring how approaches borrowed from other domains can be combined with efforts in the world of research data to help make the granting of access to data more efficient, and also more ‘focused’ (that is, to be more permissive where ‘data poisoning’ has traditionally presented a barrier to access).³⁷ These efforts show us that **in order to automate access control, fine-grained management of data—at the variable level—as well as automation of the conditions and roles of the users granting access, must be implemented.**

³⁷ See Lungley, Deidre, Gilders, Thomas, Bell, Darren, & Rumiancev, Artiom. (2022, November 30). Towards Machine-assisted Disclosure Assessment with DDI-CDI, DPV and sdcMicro. EDDI2022: The 14th Annual European DDI User Conference (EDDI2022), Sciences Po, Paris, France. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7656053>. See also the presentation from Darren Bell and Deidre Lungley at the 24 March Workshop ‘[Optimising Your Data Description for Integration and Reuse: DDI Cross-Domain Integration \(DDI-CDI\)](#)’. This was also one of the topics examined at [the recent Dagstuhl workshop](#) and has led to a CDIF WG activity, involving the UK Data Archive, the Australian Data Archive and others, to explore these issues further.

5. Data Engineering

As described in the foregoing, we are confronted with a set of significant challenges—the increase in demand for data, with accompanying metadata to make them useful—which require a change in the way that data are perceived and managed. Data can be managed and disseminated in a granular way which reflects the kind of resource it is, rather than as an adjunct to support the publication of research findings. This implies a cultural change in data stewardship, from a ‘bibliographic’ practice to a data engineering practice.³⁸ In the current ‘bibliographic’ practice, data are treated as sets of file-level packages, which are described through manual documentation processes and downloaded by researchers, who will then perform any data integration activities prior to analysis. The objective of a data engineering practice is to apply **sufficiently detailed, standardised, and interoperable metadata** to create **a network for FAIR data exchange**, which will facilitate the increased automation of fine-grained access control and cross-domain data combination, as discussed below.

This cultural change will be a difficult one. It is certainly not intended to undermine the excellent, decades-long work of existing data repositories. Nor is there likely to be sufficient cost-benefit for such an approach to be applied to all data, all the time. But we are witnessing increasing demand for research infrastructures to respond to the challenges described above. Furthermore, the energy, willingness, and requirement to undertake this transformation exists as a result of the FAIR vision, and it is one of the objectives of the Open Science movement and EOSC. Thus, from a policy perspective we are faced with both significant challenges and a significant opportunity.

To respond to these challenges and opportunities, a number of transformations will be necessary. As argued above, these rest fundamentally upon the provision of **sufficiently detailed, fine-grained, standardised, and interoperable metadata** and require **a shift from a ‘bibliographic’ data stewardship practice to a data engineering practice**. This is a shift of magnitude which will necessitate considerable resourcing, investment, and upskilling, but which will also achieve significant benefits. The objective of such a shift is to provide **a network for FAIR data exchange** which will facilitate the opportunities noted above: automated data combination for cross-domain research, automated and fine-grained access control, ultimately better enabling the use of AI. A good example of metadata facilitating a (relatively FAIR) data exchange is the use of SDMX³⁹ in the statistical and economic regulatory sector. We understand the aspiration of EOSC to achieve a ‘web of FAIR data and services’ in precisely these terms.

³⁸ Comparable arguments, albeit using different terms, were advanced in the very important article: Parsons, M.A. and Fox, P.A., 2013. Is Data Publication the Right Metaphor?. *Data Science Journal*, 12, pp.WDS32–WDS46. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.2481/dsj.WDS-042>

³⁹ Statistical Data and Metadata Exchange - <https://sdmx.org/>

6. Support for Research Infrastructures

As argued above, realising the vision and the benefits of FAIR data, particularly automating data integration and provisioning responsive and fine-grained data access, will require a number of transformations and in particular a **shift from a ‘bibliographic’ data stewardship practice to a data engineering practice**. As already noted, this is a shift of magnitude which will require considerable resourcing, investment, and upskilling; but one which will also achieve significant benefits.

Few of our research infrastructures are currently equipped to face a task of this size. Concern will be expressed by data archives and repositories that are under-resourced even for the current tasks of providing file-level metadata and digital preservation, and this is already evident in some of the discussions around FAIR and the emphasis on machine-actionability.⁴⁰

Much of the technology needed for more granular data management already exists. Many data archives have implemented ‘shopping basket’ applications where researchers can select a set of variables from across the various data sets held by the archive, and such implementations reflect a change in the way these technologies are implemented rather than a shift in the underlying technology (typically databases already in use). This change is characterised by management at the variable level, instead of solely focusing on the data set as a monolithic entity. Within WorldFAIR, we can see this in practice in the SALURBAL case⁴¹, in the INSPIRE Network case⁴², and elsewhere. Many data infrastructures are beginning to provide this type of capability (witness ODIS⁴³ and GBIF⁴⁴ which are also partners in the WorldFAIR project).

Given the preceding observations, it is essential to insist on two points. First, the transition from bibliographic data stewardship to data engineering categorically should not place an extra burden on researchers. On the contrary, this transition, if realised, will reduce that burden. Second, those infrastructures and data services that are involved in providing researchers with data (e.g. large facilities, planetary observing systems, social surveys and so on) should be adequately resourced to provide FAIR data, to serve fully integrated data products that correspond to researchers’ needs. It is through adequate resourcing and implementation of a data engineering approach described here that we can address the opportunity cost of not having FAIR data and reduce the amount of effort spent data wrangling.⁴⁵ The same applies to the so-called ‘long tail’ of research data production, including data creation or collection activities in research performing organisations, from large faculties to individual researchers: the objective should not be to turn researchers into data stewards, but to make it easier for data stewards to furnish researchers with the data they need for analysis and knowledge creation.

⁴⁰ See Mons, Barend et al. ‘Cloudy, Increasingly FAIR; Revisiting the FAIR Data Guiding Principles for the European Open Science Cloud’. 1 Jan. 2017: 49–56. <https://doi.org/10.3233/ISU-170824>. See also the Leiden Declaration on FAIR Digital Objects <https://www.fdo2022.org/programme/leiden-declaration-fdo> and Augustus, Ron, Smit, Anja, Teperek, Marta, Kok, Ruben, & Groep, David. (2022). Reaction to Leiden Declaration FDO. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7260200>

⁴¹ Quistberg DA, Diez Roux AV, Bilal U, Moore K, Ortigoza A, Rodriguez DA, Sarmiento OL, Frenz P, Friche AA, Caiaffa WT, Vives A, Miranda JJ; SALURBAL Group. Building a Data Platform for Cross-Country Urban Health Studies: the SALURBAL Study. *J Urban Health*. 2019 Apr;96(2):311-337. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11524-018-00326-0>. PMID: 30465261; PMCID: PMC6458229.

⁴² INSPIRE PEACH is based on the OMOP Common Data Model, which provides for granular specification of data for reuse: <https://aphrc.org/inspire/project/a-platform-for-evaluation-and-analysis-of-covid-19-harmonised-data-peach-2/>

⁴³ See <https://oceaninfohub.org/odis/>

⁴⁴ See <https://www.gbif.org/>

⁴⁵ The PWC report for the European Commission estimated the opportunity cost of not having FAIR data to be 10.2 Bn per annum. The report also estimated that ‘data cleansing’ or data wrangling of poor quality data ‘can take up to 80% of the total effort’, leaving only 20% of project effort for analysis. European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Cost-benefit analysis for FAIR research data: cost of not having FAIR research data, Publications Office, 2019, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/02999>

7. International Partnerships

The perspective of the WorldFAIR project is avowedly global and holds that the EC, the European Research Area and EOSC have a major role to play as part of an international science ecosystem. It is not a mere truism to observe that science is a global endeavour, with global ramifications. Similarly, standardisation efforts—particularly in science, data and metadata—need to be global.

Many of the organisations that develop and maintain specifications and standards are international and global in scope. These include treaty organisations like BIPM, large and well-resourced standards organisations like the Open Geospatial Consortium, as well as smaller entities serving particular domains, like the DDI Alliance or TDWG.⁴⁶ Some International Scientific Unions like IUPAC⁴⁷ have a particular vocation to establish and maintain standards and terminologies. Some of these entities are well-financed. Others rely extensively on volunteer effort, or time donated by researchers and data experts. Although such activities can be extremely effective, they are frequently significantly under-resourced, particularly when the passion of creating a resource gives way to the more mundane (and less visible) task of maintaining it. The challenge involved in maintaining or transitioning technical platforms, handing over leadership, or simply of financial sustainability are present for many such initiatives. Such entities have a wide range of business models, governance arrangements and juridical statuses.

The availability of funding to ensure the further development of such entities, even when they are outside the EC (on the model that led to WorldFAIR) would be extremely beneficial to European research and to EOSC. If international funding partnerships can be agreed, similar in ambition to the Belmont Forum⁴⁸, to assist data and metadata standards development, so much the better, but the EC has the capacity and mission to lead the way. **One immediate step could be a survey and analysis of business models, governance and juridical statuses along the lines of the study CODATA previously conducted with OECD on ‘Business Models for Sustainable Data Repositories’.**⁴⁹

Standards such as Schema.org, DCAT, SKOS, PROV-O, and DDI-CDI, or emergent standards or protocols such as I-ADOPT, are being suggested for the emergent CDIF.⁵⁰ These have a number of different origins and maintainers, but the prominence of web standards developed and maintained under the auspices of W3C is notable. The stability and sustainability of standards included in the CDIF will be important, and a matter of interest for EOSC and other stakeholders internationally.

As recommended in the *Turning FAIR into Reality* report, cited above, ‘Research communities need to be supported to develop interoperability frameworks that define their practices for data sharing, data formats, metadata standards, tools and infrastructure.’⁵¹ The FIPs exercises undertaken by the WorldFAIR project are a good approach and will be more effective if they are international in scope. The UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science calls on Member States and other stakeholders to promote: ‘Community agreements, concluded in the context of regional or global research communities, and which define community practices for data sharing, data formats, metadata standards, ontologies and terminologies, tools and infrastructure. International scientific unions and associations, regional or national research infrastructures and journal editorial boards each have a role to play in helping develop these agreements. In addition, convergence between the various semantic artefacts (particularly vocabularies, taxonomies, ontologies and metadata schema) is essential for the interoperability and reuse of data for interdisciplinary research.’⁵² Both CODATA and the Research Data Alliance are well-placed to coordinate such activities.

⁴⁶ BIPM <https://www.bipm.org/en/home>; OGC <https://www.ogc.org/>; DDI Alliance <https://ddialliance.org/>; TDWG <https://www.tdwg.org/>

⁴⁷ See <https://iupac.org/>

⁴⁸ See <https://www.belmontforum.org/>

⁴⁹ OECD (2017), "Business models for sustainable research data repositories", *OECD Science, Technology and Industry Policy Papers*, No. 47, OECD Publishing, Paris, <https://doi.org/10.1787/302b12bb-en>

⁵⁰ Schema.org <https://schema.org/>; DCAT <https://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-dcat-3/>; SKOS <https://www.w3.org/2004/02/skos/>; PROV-O <https://www.w3.org/TR/prov-o/>; DDI-CDI <https://ddialliance.org/Specification/ddi-cdi/>; I-ADOPT <https://i-adopt.github.io/index.html>

⁵¹ European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, *Turning FAIR into reality: final report and action plan* from the European Commission expert group on FAIR data, Publications Office, 2018, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/1524>; p.29.

⁵² UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science, VI.iii.18.f, p.24. <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000379949>

POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

1. **Sufficiently Detailed, Standardised and Interoperable Metadata:** The *sine qua non* to greater automation of cross-domain data combination and analysis *and* fine-grained and responsive access control is sufficiently detailed, standardised and interoperable metadata. There are no short cuts: data and metadata are hard. **Support is necessary for the development, adoption and implementation of standards *and* for the increased use of tools for automated metadata management.**
2. **Community FAIR Practices:** Research communities need to be encouraged and facilitated in the process of exploring, declaring and implementing the FAIR practices that are most appropriate to their domain, while of course aligning with cross-domain standards where possible. The FAIR Implementation Profiles tool and methodology provide a good framework for this activity, but further development and refinement is needed. Domain practices further require the existence of agreed standards and support for their development and use.
3. **Cross-Domain Data Combination:** Research into global challenges needs to be able to combine data from different sources, across domains and to do so in automated ways at scale. This requires **investment to improve the capacity to provide standards, tools and metadata to support cross-domain interoperability and data granularity.**
4. **Fine-Grained Access Control:** It is a legal and moral imperative that access to data be granted in an ethical manner, in line with accepted best practice. At the same time, these obligations should not present any greater barrier to reuse of data than necessary. The key to finding the right balance here is to have granular access control, so that data access can be as broad as possible, and no broader. **Systems that can support negotiation of access to data in a dynamic fashion are needed in order to responsibly meet the demand.**
5. **Data Engineering:** Achieving a network for FAIR data exchange, or the EOSC vision of ‘a web of FAIR data and services’, will require a shift from a ‘bibliographic’ practice to a data engineering practice. Without undermining the importance of data stewardship as such, policy and funding should help enable that shift, at least for those cross-domain, grand challenge research areas where automated data combination, the use of AI and fine-grained access control are pressing requirements.
6. **Support for Research Infrastructures:** A lot of attention is being paid to the task of assisting researchers with stewardship of the data they create. It is of course essential that data underpinning research findings is available as part of the record of science, hence the need for data deposit policies, data management plans and FAIR assessment tools that target individual data sets. However, **a key task of EOSC, and similar initiatives, is to ensure that research infrastructures have the capacity to partner with researchers and to provide them with the integrated or integratable data they need, upstream of analysis.** It is essential that due attention is paid therefore to the challenges of data combination, especially across domain boundaries.
7. **International Partnerships:** It is essential that EOSC engage with, and contribute to, the international development of standards, tools and metadata. **A study of business models, governance and juridical statuses of organisations that curate standards for data and metadata would be beneficial.** The creation of partnerships with authoritative international organisations or initiatives is a necessary part of building EOSC and should not be neglected. To avoid building a silo, EOSC should avoid the temptation to ‘go it alone’. On the contrary, **EOSC should actively partner with existing international data infrastructures and organisations that maintain standards and metadata schema (particularly those related to the UN data ecosystem), with inter-governmental initiatives and with global representative bodies such as the International Science Council and the International Scientific Unions.**

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